
Copenhagen, 25 March 2026

The table attached to this document specifies the features of the *Campylobacter* reference strains available at the EURL-PH-FWDB for the Network Laboratories.

The strains are provided as pure cultures in transport media, prepared from fresh passages of the reference strains. The cultures must be sub-cultured immediately after arrival to your laboratory. To prepare passages of the strains, use a sterile loop and transfer a generous amount of the culture from the vial to a medium known to support growth of thermophilic *Campylobacter* spp.. Mueller Hinton agar or broth supplemented with defibrinated blood and beta-NAD can be used. Incubate under microaerophilic conditions and store the reference strains at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

A certificate will be provided together with the reference materials.

Please note that the reference strains are provided for being used as positive controls in methods set up, for quality assurance purposes, and specific assays (e.g. determination of the serogroup, presence of virulence genes). Any other use or their distribution to other laboratories is not allowed without formal consent from the EURL-PH-FWDB.

BIOSAFETY WARNING

Campylobacter spp. are human pathogens and a common cause of gastrointestinal infection. In some cases, infection can lead to complications such as bacteraemia or post-infectious sequelae, including Guillain–Barré syndrome. Laboratory-acquired infections have been reported. Therefore, they should be handled in accordance with national biosafety guidelines for pathogenic microorganisms, and particular care must be taken when handling cultures and clinical specimens.

Annex 1. List of Campylobacter reference strains available at the EURL-PH-FWDB

Strain ID	Species	ST-type	AMR - phenotypic	AMR – genotypic – based on AMR finder plus
EURL-Camp-jejuni-01	<i>C. jejuni</i>	7433	Chloramphenicol, Ciprofloxacin, Gentamicin, Tetracycline	Genes: blaOXA-193, tet(O), aph(3')IIIa, sat4, erm(B), ant(6)-Ia Point mutations: 50S L22 A103V, gyrA T86I
EURL-Camp-coli -02	<i>C. coli</i>	872	Ciprofloxacin, Erythromycin, Tetracycline	Genes: blaOXA-489, tet(O), aadE-Cc Point mutations: gyrA T86I, 23S A2075G